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BEHAVIOURAL STUDY OF ZOO ANIMALS

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Abstract

The behaviour of zoo animals differs from their conspecifics in the wild. Understanding behaviour is a key for better husbandry and management. Behaviour defined, and behavioural sampling methods like Ad libitum sampling, Focal sampling, All occurrence sampling, one zero sampling and instantaneous sampling methods for qualitative and quantitative measurement of behaviours were described in this communication. Besides, various methods for development of ethogram, behavioural categories were explained. The role of this behavioural study was to describe the activity pattern, behavioural need, stress, welfare effect of environmental enrichment on stereotypic behaviour, and captive breeding of zoo animals. The significance of behavioural studies in zoo conditions in understanding of species biology, promoting husbandry, breeding and welfare were discussed. Limitations in behavioural research and insurmountable difficulties in zoos discussed. Suggestions were made for collaborative research and scientific management of zoos.

Key Words Behaviour, Captivity, Zoo, Ethogram, Sampling method, Activity pattern

1. Introduction

Zoo animals are wild animals in captivity. They are maintained in zoos for education, conservation, research, and recreation (Mench & Kreger, 1996). Behaviour is the exhibition of a phenotypic trait within the environmental context for which primary selective forces have shaped it, the outcome of which being maximal, inclusive fitness (Eisenberg, 1981). Behaviour includes all the processes by which an animal responds to stimuli in its environment. Behavioural studies in captivity provide important information on the physical and psychological wellbeing and reproductive status of the animal necessary for their propagation. These studies include the monitoring of baseline behaviour (e.g. maintenance behaviours) or a change in instances (e.g. in response to environmental enrichments)

using appropriate behavioural sampling techniques. A complete understanding of phenotypic traits of a species requires a combination of long-term field studies with observations and experiments on their captive counterparts. Field studies allow the formulation of realistic hypotheses but have the disadvantage that they do not allow the complete control of many potential confounding variables (Lambrechts *et al.*, 1999). So, studies with captive animals are important because they allow tests and observations that cannot be conducted in the field. Experiments with captive animals have the disadvantage, as the artificial environment may provoke abnormal behaviour (Dawkins, 1998). In zoo contexts, behavioural research usually focused towards collecting baseline information and addressing

management problems. Both are important and contribute in their way to understand the biology of animals and their conservation. This communication gives a generalized account on the significance of behavioural study in management and breeding of zoo animals.

2. Measuring behaviour

Behaviour of an animal is studied to understand the animal and the species. Behavioural study not only describes the behaviours displayed by the animals, but also asks questions regarding what, who, why, where and when the patterns in question occur (Lehner, 1996). Such study may include a description of behaviours in form of ethogram, estimation of activity time, behavioural bout and average time spent in different behaviours, seasonal variation of behaviours and effect of environmental parameters on it. Preliminary data collection is of importance as this provides baseline information to plan and project the detailed research work. Methodology of recording behavioural data depends on the question in hand and selection of appropriate sampling technique having accuracy, repeatability and relevance to the study. Depending on the research question, observers may record environmental parameters (e.g., temperature, humidity, intensity of light, rainfall), space utilization and seasonal variation in behaviour. There are two research methods used in the study of behaviour. Both methods are useful and have unique characteristics that help determine when each one is more suitable.

The first method, qualitative analysis, seeks to understand the behaviour of an animal in descriptive terms. Usually without the use of any numerical analysis, qualitative ethology presents a holistic view of animal behaviour. It is a common approach taken by scientists who study ecological aspects of animal behaviour in the wild. This qualitative ethology is especially useful when 1) the animal being examined

is a new species whose behaviour is unknown, 2) when the animal is exhibiting previously unobserved behaviours, and 3) when the observer wishes to develop a narrative explanation of behaviour, an ethogram (Mohapatra & Panda, 2014a). Better explanations and descriptions of behaviour of animals help better understanding and prediction.

The second method, quantitative analysis, is an experimental approach to ethology. It requires collection of numerically analysable data about the behaviour of animals. These data can then be used to make concrete statements about how animals behave. Quantitative analysis is considered the most useful method to learn about animal behaviour today, and it is different in many ways from qualitative analysis. One crucial difference is the amount of work required of the researcher prior to the observation of behaviour (Mohapatra & Panda, 2013). Quantitative analysis requires much forethought and planning of any successful behavioural study. Details of behavioural data collection methodology including ethogram, sampling methods are described.

2.1 Ethogram

An ethogram is “a complete inventory of the behaviour patterns of a species” (Tinbergen, 1951). An animal’s behaviour is naturally a continuous flow from one event or state to another. Martin and Bateson (1993) defines “event” as a short behaviour pattern like movement of the body or sound production at a particular point of time. The important feature of an event is in its frequency of repetition. A “state” is a long behaviour pattern or prolonged activity, e.g. resting, sleeping or near to any object. Often, the most important characteristic of a state is its time duration (Martin & Bateson, 1993). Breaking it down into categories allows a researcher to make measurements and comparisons. This is also useful for understanding the behavioural repertoire

of a species and for recording behaviour easier. When developing a catalogue of behaviours, names are applied to behaviours with an implicit description. Familiarity with the animal's behaviour and insights into its function help to understand the complexity of what an animal does.

2.2. Describing Behaviour

It can be based on physical form and structure of the behaviour in terms of posture, movement and sound or on the presumed effects of the subject's behaviour on itself, on its environment, or on other organisms or basing on spatial relation i.e., where or with whom the subject is interacting? Behavioural description must be clear, precise and comparable with those collected by other researchers, without any anthropomorphic interpretation. Therefore, a preliminary study and the drawing of an ethogram can be a great help.

There are two types of behavioural descriptions: empirical and functional descriptions (Lehner, 1996; Martin & Bateson, 1993). The empirical description deals with the structure, posture and body movement e.g. "tiger licking its body hairs with its tongue." Empirical description is useful in preliminary studies and constructing an ethogram. The functional description is an account of the behavioural movements and function e.g. "tiger is grooming."

2.3. Behavioural categories

Each behaviour is represented by a range of several movements and postures, making it difficult to obtain a definitive measurement. It is advisable to split behaviours into categories for easy collection and with precision. For example, to describe and measure the resting behaviour, it is better to divide this activity into its various components: resting awake, sleeping, roll over and laying on back etc. Martin and Bateson (1993) suggested features such as number, definition, independence and homogeneity for behavioural categories.

Number: It should have a complete description to indicate the assigned behavioural patterns in accordance to the research objectives.

Definition: It should be objective, clear, concise and complete.

Independence: It should be independent so that a behaviour pattern can be assigned to it without any ambiguity.

Homogeneity: All behaviour patterns included in a category should have similar features.

2.4. Sampling Methods

There are many methods of sampling to obtain a true picture of behaviour. It is not possible, also not necessary to record all types of behaviours. Most behaviours are classified as events or states lasting an appreciable amount of time, which can summarize the occurrence of both with counts or frequencies. There are following sampling techniques for behavioural data collection.

2.4.1. Ad Libitum (ad lib) Sampling: It is an informal method of sampling while making field notes (Altmann, 1974). As the observer can't record all behaviours and there may be observational bias in recording the behavioural pattern, it is difficult to get reliable quantitative information based on Ad libitum. However, this method helps in the development of ethograms and studying rare behaviours. Das (1980) described reproductive behaviours of captive tigers following ad lib sampling. Besides, observations on rare but significant behaviours like egg laying and territoriality in reptiles were collected using ad lib sampling (Bustard and Maharana, 1982; Maharana and Pati, 1983). Mohapatra and Panda (2014a) developed the ethogram of Indian pangolins following this sampling method.

2.4.2. Focal Animal Sampling: Focal behavioural sampling records all occurrences of specified actions

of one individual during a predetermined period (e.g., one hour) (Altmann, 1974). The observer also records the length of the sample period and the amount of time the focal animal is in view. It provides unbiased data relevant to a wide array of questions if the study animal remains in the field of view. The method has been used for studying mating behaviours (Mohapatra et al. 2015a, 2015b), stereotypic behaviour of zoo animals (Vaz. & Narayan, 2017). Mohapatra and Panda (2013) used the method for standardization of instantaneous sampling intervals.

2.4.3. All Occurrence Sampling: It focuses on a particular behaviour instead of a particular individual e.g. number of alarm calls in monkey troop. It is also useful for providing the frequency of behaviour in the group as a whole. This method is suitable for studying the behavioural synchrony within a group (Altmann, 1974). Behaviours like sexual mounting and grooming can be successfully scored by using this method but behaviours like 'avert gaze' or similar brief or subtle responses cannot be scored following this method. The result will degrade in case of large group size and space occupied (Bernstein, 1991).

2.4.4. One-Zero Sampling: The sampling method records an occurrence or non-occurrence (rather than frequency) of the behaviour in each sampling period. An observer makes single entry during a predetermined time unit if any instance of behaviour of interest is seen during that time unit regardless of its duration or number of times it occurs (Bernstein, 1991). It can provide good indication about the rate of occurrence of behaviour per unit time (e.g. hourly rate). But if the observer is interested in recording frequency and duration of behaviours and percent of time spent in various states as variables of interest, alternative sampling methods like focal and instantaneous sampling methods should be considered (Altmann, 1974).

2.4.5. Instantaneous or Scan Sampling: It is a method of recording behaviour as it occurs in a predetermined time or as the sample is in the act of doing it. It is used to study the percent of time spent in a certain activity. If the behaviours of all members of a group are surveyed within a short period of time, it is called a scan sampling. This provides data on the distribution of behavioural states in a group. Instantaneous or scan sampling is for sampling of easily identifiable behaviours. The sample intervals should be ideally shorter than the behaviour of interest.

After collection of behavioural data following a suitable sampling method, appropriate statistical methods are used for analysis. The sampling method was used to collect activity pattern, seasonal variation in behaviour, evaluation of environmental enrichment programmes for Indian pangolins and tiger (Mohapatra *et al.* 2010, 2014; Mohapatra & Panda, 2013; Mohapatra *et al.*, 2016), behavioural correlates for breeding in Indian black buck (Rajagopal, *et al.*, 2011; Archunana & Rajagopal, 2013), effect of enrichment, personality and life history on the welfare of Asiatic lions (Goswami *et al.*, 2020, 2021), stereotypic behaviour of giraffes (Kulkarni, 2020) and influence of zoo visitors on Indian gaur (Sekar & Rajagopal, 2008).

3. Significance of behavioural study of zoo animals

The missions of the zoos are complex but generally include conservation, education, research and recreation. Zoos are making a difference for wildlife conservation by bringing people face-to-face with living animals and inspiring them to care about and care for the natural world. The management of captive animals requires basic knowledge of the needs and information about its reproduction. However, this information is often lacking in endangered species (Wildt *et al.*, 2003). Zoos offer

unique opportunities to study animal behaviour, physiology, growth, development of a wide variety of taxa under semi-controlled conditions. Many of these studies would be difficult, if not impossible, to conduct in nature because of practical and ethical limitations. Behavioural studies in zoos provide valuable information about the inhabitants ultimately contributing towards a better understanding of species biology, promoting husbandry and welfare of the animals. The particular method of behavioural study preferred in zoo condition, as it is easily observed, non-invasive, and non-intrusive measure of welfare and can provide good cues about the internal, subjective state of animals, with their preferences and needs (Mench & Mason, 1997; Dawkins, 2004). Behavioural studies in zoos are usually carried out on the following aspects.

3.1. Ethogram, time budget and activity pattern

Ethogram represents behavioural repertoire of animals. This is essential for starting a behavioural study focusing on a species or specific behavioural category (Mohapatra & Panda, 2013; Mohapatra & Panda 2014a). The time budget in the behavioural repertoire is a reflection of resources (Young, 2003), thus the pattern of activity and time budget is an important basis for understanding behaviour. Hence, behavioural studies can be an important element for successful captive management of a species (Kleiman, 1994). These can be even more crucial for developing effective conservation strategies in many species. Studies of free ranging animals are often hampered by the difficulty of direct observation of the subjects (Emmons, 1988; Law *et al.*, 1997). For example, scientific study of captive felids is equally applicable to the conservation of wild felids as well (Law *et al.*, 1997). Study of activity pattern and time budget are essential to know the baseline activity and change of the same in positive and negative state of welfare by exhibiting stereotypic behaviour or increased

exploration in response to enrichment (Mohapatra *et al.*, 2010; Mohapatra *et al.*, 2014).

3.2. Behavioural needs

Behavioural needs are activities that individual animals of a species in captivity show a strong motivation to perform, and which may lead to frustration, stress, health problems and/or abnormal behaviours when they are hindered. A comparison of the natural behaviour in captivity helps assessment of positive and negative welfare states of the animal. Besides, the display of abnormal behaviour or natural behaviour in irregular frequency indicates disturbance (Mench & Mason, 1997). When control systems are overtaxed and there is an actual or potential reduction in fitness, the animal is stressed (Broom & Johnson, 1993). Therefore, behavioural study must include not only the observation of what animals do, but also examination of general biological activities that help to form and develop an animal's behaviour. Regular observations help understanding what animal wants to fulfill its biological needs. It also facilitates chalk out management strategies to address the issues.

3.3. Animal welfare, environmental enrichment and space utilization

Animals continuously explore their environment to stay aware of food and water sources, shelters, trails, predators, hazards, territory intruders and potential mates. Zoo animals are typically maintained in static environments and have limited opportunities to explore (Mench, 1998). The ability of a species to respond to captive conditions with behaviour from its normal repertoire depends on the degree to which the particular captive condition resembles its natural environment (Carlstead & Shepherdson, 1994). The use of behaviour in stress and welfare assessment is based on knowledge of normal species-specific behaviour as well as on the nature of deviations in response to different stimuli and emotions (Keeling &

Jensen, 2002; Squires, 2003). The zoo community was among the first to raise concerns over abnormal and stereotypic behaviors in captive animals and began developing environmental enrichment strategies to deal with the perceived problem (Swaigood & Shepherdson, 2005). Stereotypies are relatively invariant, repetitive behaviors that seem to have no immediate function (Mason, 1991). Useful behaviours for welfare assessment include activity levels, posture and movement patterns, vocalization, aggression, sleep patterns and ingestion (Squires, 2003). They may not have the motivation, opportunity or need to display the range of behaviours necessary to succeed in its natural habitat (McPhee, 2002).

In the zoo community, environmental enrichment has become almost an accepted method for husbandry with specific aim of improving wellbeing and as such is the method of choice for reducing stereotypic behaviour (Swaigood & Shepherdson, 2005). Any object or stimulus that attracts the animals' interest can be considered as an environmental enrichment (Shepherdson et al., 1998). It is generally designed to permit the animals to display their natural behavioural repertoire (Mellen & MacPhee, 2001). Increasing physical and temporal complexity may add biologically relevant information to an animal's enclosure, resulting in increased opportunities for exploration. It can also offer an animal to learn and achieve a desired goal through the performance of appropriate behaviour (Sambrook & Buchanan-Smith, 1997). Animal enclosures can be enriched by simply adding appropriate substrates such as sand, dirt or vegetation. The substrates can also induce foraging and exploratory behaviour by hiding food, adding scents or naturally occurring life forms e.g. insects. Proper hideouts and landscaping can offer privacy, encourage territoriality, give escape gateways, and therefore can make scope for better social interactions. Climbing structures allow more efficient use of

space and provide shade and temperature gradients for choice of microclimate. They can also provide hiding places from conspecifics, the visitors, and zoo keepers. Novel objects like toys and cardboard box, scents, and exhibit changes are techniques used to stimulate exploratory behaviour. Zoo biologists now accept the responsibility to design programmes and techniques carefully that will contribute to the 'psychological well-being' and enhance the lifestyles of captive animals. Behavioural observation before and during environmental enrichment sessions are useful to develop the baseline behavioural budget and to evaluate the behavioural response of the animals to the enrichment object, respectively.

It is important to assess how the animal is using the enclosure in relation to the available space and/or the ecological resources of the enclosure. There are two methods usually used for this purpose. Firstly, by dividing enclosures into several equal area zones and calculating Spread Partition Index of those areas to find any difference in observed occupancy time or frequency compared to the expected time or frequency (Mallapur *et al.* 2005). Secondly, dividing the enclosure based on the resource value (may be of unequal area) and calculating the utilization time/frequency of specific resources in relation to its overall availability in that resource (Lechowicz, 1982).

3.4. Captive breeding programme

Many endangered species are currently involved in conservation breeding programs worldwide. Conservation breeding deals with propagation of captive populations, often with the ultimate aim of releasing animals into the wild. Zoos provide an opportunity to determine the behavioural patterns associated with reproduction of many elusive endangered animals that are difficult to study in the wild. Research estimating parameters such as age, onset of oestrus, duration of oestrus, inter oestrus

duration, breeding season, mating behaviour, courtship, copulation, post copulatory aggression, gestation period, litter size, interbirth interval, weaning age and weight, behaviour of primiparous mother with infants and needs of lactating mother have inherent benefit in management, breeding and propagation of endangered species in captivity (Das, 1980; Bustard & Maharana, 1980; Maharana & Bustard, 1981; Mohapatra & Panda, 2014a,b; Mohapatra *et al.*, 2016; Mohapatra, 2016). Study of behavioural aspects for conservation breeding is useful in maintenance of the available small population to make self-sustaining viable populations in captivity without compromising the success of reintroductions. The need for behavioural studies to improve husbandry and management for breeding endangered species has been highlighted (Håkansson, 2007; Mohapatra & Panda, 2014b; Sutherland, 1998). Behavioural study gives crucial insights on animals' biology needed for conservation breeding (Bustard & Maharana, 1980; Maharana & Bustard, 1981; Mohapatra & Panda, 2014b). With the technological advancement, installation of infra-red enabled CCTV cameras provide important biological information of nocturnal and elusive species like Indian pangolins greatly help in their conservation breeding programme in zoo (Mohapatra, 2016; Mohapatra & Panda, 2013).

4. Limitations in behavioural research in zoos

The zoo, as a living laboratory, presents a unique and valuable avenue for research. It often lacks special facilities and financial support to carry out serious research on behaviour. Zoo animals are kept in an artificial environment with less opportunity to display their natural behaviours. Though the conditions have improved in many zoos where animals are displayed in large naturalist enclosures simulating their natural habitat for fulfilment of their biological needs, still some zoos exhibit in small artificial environments like cages. Besides, in zoo conditions many events like

feed, feeding time, visitor's presence and interaction with zookeeper are predictable events for animals and can impact their behaviour (Mohapatra *et al.*, 2010). In zoos, sample size is usually small and when several groups of multiple zoological institutions are considered for study to get a larger sample size, other variables like housing conditions, husbandry practices, group composition create inter-group differences. In addition, observer does not have control over variables like time of feeding, movement of animal from exhibit to back kraal and vice versa, presence of zoo visitors and other animals (e.g. free living monkeys) that impact the exhibition of behaviour in unpredictable and undesirable ways (Hosey, 1997). At times, there is a possibility of addition (acquisition, birth and introduction) or reduction (separation, death and disposal) of animals during the study period. Besides, empirical research needs manipulation of variables. The most important difficulty is the reluctance of zoos to allow experimental manipulation of their animals or cages (Hosey, 1997). Such difficulties in zoo-based research could be overcome by considerable negotiation, cooperation, good will of both parties and collaborative research. Choosing a research subject which helps to solve management problems that encourage carrying out research in zoos. Above all, adopting non-invasive methodology and following legal and ethical standards rationalize the study.

5. Conclusion

Zoo has the potential for development of a database for efficient management of wild animals in captivity. The observations can be safely extrapolated to nature if enclosure enrichment simulates near to their habitat. Ultimately, zoos can contribute immensely to standard research on a wide range of topics, both on pure and applied fields, in collaboration with reputed research institutes with minimum financing for zoo management on scientific lines.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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